

Master's thesis in Theoretical Physics

DOUBLY SPECIAL RELATIVITY

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Abstract

In this thesis, the program of Doubly Special Relativity (DSR) is reported. DSR is a relativistic theory in which a short length scale, possibly Planckian, is an observer-independent scale in addition to the speed of light. This theory agrees with special relativity at large distances or low energies. There are two most studied models of DSR theory : DSR1, proposed by Amelino-Camelia and DSR2 proposed by Smolin and Magueijo. After constructing these models, this theory was found to be emergent from De Sitter momentum space where the curvature radius coincides with the new invariant scale. A proposal of an extension of DSR theory to general relativity, passing through a generalized form of DSR2, has been made by Smolin and Magueijo, the so-called gravity's rainbow.

Introduction

Special relativity (SR) taught us that the relativity principle coexists in harmony with the observer-independence of the speed of light as this was successfully tested by several experiments with great accuracy. This theory was built for the sake of reconciling electromagnetic phenomena with classical mechanics where the Michelson-Morley experiment played an important role in emphasizing the constancy of propagation of light. It is characterized by several effects such as time dilatation and length contraction and it forces to abandon certain classical concepts such as absolute time and absolute space and it serves a good understanding of relativistic particle processes. Its generalization has led to a crucial investigation for explaining gravitation as a manifestation of curved spacetime. It has also an essential role as a background of field theory, to mention as well the important position that the representation of Poincaré group has in classifying particles and so on...

However, SR was tested only in the domain of low energies in reference to Planck energy or large distances compared to the Planck length. These later are obtained from combining the fundamental constants : c , the speed of light, G , the gravitational constant, and \hbar the Planck constant and often assumed to play an important role in spacetime structure according to quantum-gravity research as they represent thresholds beyond which quantum-gravity effects are expected to appear, although there is a lacking experimental information about this scale. There is also, apparently, what is called the cosmic ray paradox which, briefly speaking, indicates that some astrophysics experimental results disagree with SR predictions joining the path of quantum-gravity studies for suggesting that the dispersion relation should be modified at Planck scale.

From an exploratory point of view, it is interesting to modify the postulates of SR by relaxing one of them or expanding them by adding one or several postulates and see what happens and if the relativity principle, which has served physics to successfully progress for hundreds of years, is about to be preserved then one has to have a free but a careful choice concerning which postulates go along with it, and then learn from nature with what the relativity principle coexists and how.

The remarks above concerning quantum-gravity research and cosmic ray paradox pushed Amelino-Camelia to construct a relativistic theory with two observer-independent scales: the speed of light and the Planck length or energy, it is called Doubly Special Relativity. After that, Smolin and Magueijo have constructed another type of DSR theory and these ideas attracted several research groups to investigate on them further from different perspectives, whether on finding a mathematical formalism compatible with DSR theory or contributing to solve certain puzzling aspects in DSR program...etc

The thesis is organized as follows: The material is divided into four chapters, the first two chapters consist of a review of special and general relativity. Chapter 3 concerns the construction of DSR theory along with a mathematical formalism appropriate to describe it. Finally, chapter 4 deals with gravity's rainbow, an extension of DSR to general relativity. In each one of these two last chapters, an introduction is provided to state the motivations, and a conclusion is given to set some remarks and report the issues and open problems that it encounters.

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Chapter 1

Special Relativity

1.1 Principles

Special relativity theory was proposed by Einstein (1905). It is governed by the following principles :

- The relativity principle : All physical laws have the same forms in any inertial system.
- The speed of light c is an observer-independent scale.

According to these principles, time finds itself as a new coordinate, meaning that each inertial system should calibrate the ratio of distance and time in order for light to have a constant speed independently of observers :

$$-c^2 dt^2 + dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 = -c^2 dt'^2 + dx'^2 + dy'^2 + dz'^2$$

1.2 Minkowski space, Poincaré and Lorentz groups

Spacetime of SR is called the Minkowski space $M_4 \equiv (\mathbb{R}^4, \eta)$, where the tensor metric η is a Minkowskian metric, $\eta = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$, satisfying some properties:

Consider two vectors U and V in M_4 , the properties of the Minkowskian metric η are

- $\eta(U, V) = \eta(V, U)$
- If $\eta(U, V) = 0$ for $\forall U$, then $V = 0$.

Note that the second property weakens the positive-definite condition i.e. for nonzero V , $\eta(U, V)$ could be either positive or negative.

A point x in M_4 is called an *event*, for a coordinate system O_i , $x_i = (ct_i, x_i^1, x_i^2, x_i^3)$.

Taking an infinitesimal displacement and using the coordinate system O_i ,

$$U = dx_i^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^\mu} 1.$$

$$ds^2 = \eta(U, U) = \eta\left(dx_i^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^\mu}, dx_i^\nu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^\nu}\right) = dx_i^\mu dx_i^\nu \eta\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^\mu}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^\nu}\right) = \eta_{\mu\nu} dx_i^\mu dx_i^\nu$$

From the principles, ds^2 is required to be invariant in a class of coordinate systems called inertial systems, $[S_i]$.

Let S_i be an inertial coordinate system, then $[S_i] = \{S_j/x_j = px_i, p \in \text{Poincare group } P\}$

$$p = (a, \Lambda)$$

$$P : x_i \rightarrow x_j = (a, \Lambda).x_i := \Lambda x_i + a$$

In components :

$$x_j^\mu = \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu x_i^\nu + a^\mu$$

Where $p' * p = (a', \Lambda') * (a, \Lambda) := (a' + \Lambda' a, \Lambda' \Lambda)$, inverse element $p^{-1} = (-\Lambda^{-1} a, \Lambda^{-1})$, unity element: $e = (0, I)$

$\Lambda \in O(3, 1) = \{\Lambda \in GL(4, \mathbb{R}) | \Lambda \eta \Lambda^T = \eta\}$ called the complete Lorentz group and a^μ are constant parameters of spacetime translation.

Classification of Lorentz transformations

From the condition $\Lambda \eta \Lambda^T = \eta$, we get

$$(\det \Lambda)^2 = 1$$

and

$$(\Lambda^0{}_0)^2 = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^3 (\Lambda^i{}_0)^2 \geq 1$$

This shows that there exist four distinct classes of Lorentz transformations :

$O_+^\uparrow = \{\Lambda \in O(3, 1) | \det \Lambda = 1, \Lambda^0{}_0 \geq 1\} \equiv SO^\uparrow(3, 1)$, it is called the proper-orthochronous Lorentz group.

$O_-^\uparrow = \{\Lambda \in O(3, 1) | \det \Lambda = -1, \Lambda^0{}_0 \geq 1\}$ improper-orthochronous

$O_+^\downarrow = \{\Lambda \in O(3, 1) | \det \Lambda = 1, \Lambda^0{}_0 \leq -1\}$ proper-nonorthochronous

$O_-^\downarrow = \{\Lambda \in O(3, 1) | \det \Lambda = -1, \Lambda^0{}_0 \leq -1\}$ improper-nonorthochronous

Note : Proper is for subgroups with $\det \Lambda = 1$, because it does not contain spatial reflections ($\det \Lambda = -1, \Lambda^0{}_0 \geq 1$) or time reflections ($\det \Lambda = -1, \Lambda^0{}_0 \leq -1$) and

¹Notation: Einstein summation convention is adopted and Greek indices take values 0,1,2,3 while Latin indices take values 1,2,3. This notation will be used throughout the thesis.

it contains the identity ; orthochronous is for subgroups with $\Lambda^0_0 \geq 1$ because it preserves the time direction, $ct_j = \Lambda^0_0 ct_i + \dots$

1.3 Scalars, vectors/covectors and tensors in Minkowski space, covariant formulation

Scalars :

Scalars are invariant by Lorentz transformation. If a is a scalar, described in an inertial system S_i as a_i and in another inertial system S_j as a_j , then

$$a_i = a_j$$

4-vectors :

A vector V in M_4 is written as

$$V = V_i^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^\mu} = V_j^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j^\mu}$$

Hence its components transform as follows

$$V_j^\mu = \Lambda^\mu_{\nu} V_i^\nu$$

covectors:

A covector w is written as

$$w = w_{i_\mu} dx_i^\mu = w_{j_\mu} dx_j^\mu$$

its components transform as follows

$$w_{j_\mu} = \Lambda^{-1\alpha}_{\mu} w_{i_\alpha}$$

Tensors :

A tensor t of type (p,q) is written as

$$t = t_i^{\mu_1 \dots \mu_p}{}_{\nu_1 \dots \nu_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^{\mu_1}} \dots \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i^{\mu_p}} dx_i^{\nu_1} \dots dx_i^{\nu_q} = t_j^{\mu_1 \dots \mu_p}{}_{\nu_1 \dots \nu_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j^{\mu_1}} \dots \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j^{\mu_p}} dx_j^{\nu_1} \dots dx_j^{\nu_q}$$

its components transform as follows

$$t_j^{\mu_1 \dots \mu_p}{}_{\nu_1 \dots \nu_q} = \Lambda^{\mu_1}_{\alpha_1} \dots \Lambda^{\mu_p}_{\alpha_p} \Lambda^{-1\beta_1}_{\nu_1} \dots \Lambda^{-1\beta_q}_{\nu_q} t_i^{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_p}{}_{\beta_1 \dots \beta_q}$$

Remark : only tensors of the same type can form a vector space.

Lorentz indices are lowered and raised by means of η , this can be seen from the fact that there is a one-to-one correspondance between 4-vectors and covectors :

$$\eta(\cdot, \cdot) : V \rightarrow \eta(V, \cdot) \text{ where } \eta(V, \cdot) \text{ is a covector since } \eta(V, U) : U \rightarrow \eta(V, U) \in \mathbb{R}$$

So given a vector V , this corresponds to covector $w = \eta(V, \cdot)$, which is allowed by the isomorphism $\eta(\cdot, \cdot)$. Thus $V_\alpha = \eta_{\alpha\beta} V^\beta$ and $U^\alpha = \eta^{\alpha\beta} U_\beta$ with $\eta_{\mu\alpha} \eta^{\alpha\nu} = \delta_\mu^\nu$.

Covariant formulation :

Given an equation, its terms are said to be *covariant* if they transform in the same way under Lorentz transformation, we say therefore that the equation is invariant under Lorentz transformation. So it is possible to verify the invariance of a physical law under Lorentz transformation by inspecting if its terms are covariant i.e. if its terms are tensors of the same type.

An equality between scalars, vectors and in general an equality between tensors of the same type

$$t_i^{\mu_1 \dots \mu_p}{}_{\nu_1 \dots \nu_q} = c_i^{\mu_1 \dots \mu_p}{}_{\nu_1 \dots \nu_q}$$

will necessarily preserve its form when tensors are transformed

$$\Lambda^{\mu_1}{}_{\alpha_1} \dots \Lambda^{\mu_p}{}_{\alpha_p} \Lambda^{-1\beta_1}{}_{\nu_1} \dots \Lambda^{-1\beta_q}{}_{\nu_q} t_i^{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_p}{}_{\beta_1 \dots \beta_q} = \Lambda^{\mu_1}{}_{\alpha_1} \dots \Lambda^{\mu_p}{}_{\alpha_p} \Lambda^{-1\beta_1}{}_{\nu_1} \dots \Lambda^{-1\beta_q}{}_{\nu_q} c_i^{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_p}{}_{\beta_1 \dots \beta_q}$$

i.e.

$$t_j^{\mu_1 \dots \mu_p}{}_{\nu_1 \dots \nu_q} = c_j^{\mu_1 \dots \mu_p}{}_{\nu_1 \dots \nu_q}$$

1.4 Kinematics and Dynamics

4-vectors in M_4 , $U = U^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial x^0} + U^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1} + U^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2} + U^3 \frac{\partial}{\partial x^3}$, are classified into three classes,

- i/ $\eta(U, U) > 0 \rightarrow U$ is space-like
- ii/ $\eta(U, U) = 0 \rightarrow U$ is light-like
- iii/ $\eta(U, U) < 0 \rightarrow U$ is time-like

A world line is a path $x = x(t)$ of a mass point in M_4 , its tangent vector $V = \frac{dx^\mu}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}$ is time-like,

$$\eta(V, V) = -c^2 + \mathbf{v}^2$$

Where \mathbf{v} is a classical velocity.

The proper time parameter τ is defined by,

$$d\tau^2 := -\frac{ds^2}{c^2} = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) dt^2$$

The Lorentz factor γ is defined by,

$$\gamma := \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

τ is the time measured in an inertial system S' moving with the particle since $d\mathbf{x}' = 0$ in this system and $d\tau = \sqrt{dt^2 - d\mathbf{x} \cdot d\mathbf{x}} = dt'$. As a consequence, a particle seem to take longer to decay, when viewed from an inertial system which is not traveling with it. (time dilatation)

A velocity 4-vector is defined as the tangent vector to the world line parametrized by the proper time. In an inertial system

$$u =: \frac{dx}{d\tau} = \begin{bmatrix} c \frac{dt}{d\tau} \\ \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{d\tau} \end{bmatrix} = \gamma \begin{bmatrix} c \\ \mathbf{v} \end{bmatrix}$$

The momentum 4-vector is by definition $P =: mu$, where m is the mass, in an inertial system

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} mc\gamma \\ m\gamma\mathbf{v} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P^2 = \eta(P, P) = -m^2c^2$$

If the classical momentum is defined by $\mathbf{p} = m\gamma\mathbf{v}$, then

$$P^2 = -m^2c^2\gamma^2 + \mathbf{p}^2$$

Hence

$$m^2c^2\gamma^2 = m^2c^2 + \mathbf{p}^2$$

By generalization, the acceleration 4-vector is $\frac{du}{d\tau}$. The corresponding force 4-vector is defined by

$$f := \frac{dP}{d\tau} = \frac{d(mu)}{d\tau}$$

Thus

$$f = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d(mc\gamma)}{d\tau} \\ \gamma \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{d\tau} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma \frac{d(mc\gamma)}{dt} \\ \gamma \mathbf{f}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_0 \\ \gamma \mathbf{f}_c \end{bmatrix}$$

Where $\mathbf{f}_c := \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt}$ is the classical force and f_0 is the time component of f .

We have $\frac{d\eta(P, P)}{d\tau} = 0$ which implies $\eta\left(\frac{dP}{d\tau}, P\right) = 0$, thus

$$\eta(f, u) = 0 = -cf_0\gamma + \gamma\mathbf{f}_c \cdot \gamma\mathbf{v}$$

and so

$$f_0 = c^{-1}\gamma\mathbf{f}_c \cdot \mathbf{v}$$

From this, we get

$$\frac{d(mc\gamma)}{d\tau} = c^{-1}\mathbf{f}_c \cdot \mathbf{v}$$

or

$$d(mc^2\gamma) = \mathbf{f}_c \cdot d\mathbf{x}$$

which is an element of work done by the classical force. It is the energy imparted to the particle. As a result, there is an equivalence between energy and mass $E = mc^2\gamma$, the **dispersion relation** is then

$$E^2 = m^2c^4 + c^2p^2$$

$mc^2 = E_0$ is the rest energy.

As a result also

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E}{c} \\ \mathbf{p} \end{bmatrix}$$

Special relativity unites the energy and the classical momentum into the momentum 4-vector.

Conservation rules of energy-momentum

As any conserved quantity, the conservation of energy-momentum is associated with a symmetry, namely the spacetime translation symmetry. It is required that all inertial systems should agree on whether or not a certain process is physical (allowed), in other words, these rules should be invariant in all inertial systems. In SR, for a collision process of type $ab \rightarrow cd$, these rules are expressed as follows

$$P_a + P_b - P_c - P_d = 0$$

in an inertial system

$$P_a^\mu + P_b^\mu - P_c^\mu - P_d^\mu = 0 \rightarrow \begin{cases} E_a + E_b - E_c - E_d = 0 \\ p_a + p_b - p_c - p_d = 0 \end{cases}$$

1.5 Special Lorentz transformation and velocity composition

Consider two inertial systems S and S' . S' is in uniform motion with a velocity v along the x direction with respect to S , so that $y = y'$ and $z = z'$. A light pulse emitted in their common origin at $t = t' = 0$ satisfies

$$-c^2 dt^2 + dx^2 = -c^2 dt'^2 + dx'^2$$

with solution

$$x' = x \cosh\phi - ct \sinh\phi$$

$$ct' = -x \sinh\phi + ct \cosh\phi$$

ϕ here is the boost parameter or the rapidity. The origin of S' ($x'=0$) is moving with velocity v along the x axis i.e. $\frac{x}{t} = v = c \tanh\phi$ or $\frac{v}{c} = \tanh\phi$

putting

$$\gamma = \cosh\phi$$

$$\sinh\phi = \frac{v}{c}\gamma$$

The special Lorentz transformation known as a "boost" in the (xt) plane are then

$$\begin{aligned}x' &= \gamma(x - vt) \\t' &= \gamma\left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2}\right) \\y' &= y \\z' &= z\end{aligned}$$

Remark: if $v \ll c$, the Galilean transformation is recovered.

Velocity composition

We have

$$\begin{aligned}dx' &= \gamma(dx - vdt) \\dt' &= \gamma\left(dt - \frac{v}{c^2}dx\right) \\dy' &= dy \\dz' &= dz\end{aligned}$$

A particle has a velocity $v_1 = \frac{dx}{dt}$ in S, while in S' it has a velocity $v_2 = \frac{dx'}{dt'}$. From the special Lorentz transformation

$$v_2 = \frac{v_1 - v}{1 - \frac{vv_1}{c^2}}$$

If that particle is a photon, it will have the same speed c in both S and S'.

Length contraction

From special Lorentz transformation, it can be seen that a moving system S' sees a "fixed" length contracted: Taking a length of rod to be $x=l$ in the system S, the position of the ends of the rod must be measured simultaneously at $t'=0$, we get

$$l' = \frac{l}{\gamma}$$

Time dilation

An event with coordinates $(x = 0, t = T)$ in the system S will have S' coordinates satisfying

$$T' = \gamma T$$

moving systems will observe "fixed" clocks ticking slowly.

e.g. if a particle is at rest with respect to the system S, it will take longer to decay in S' than in S.

1.6 General Lorentz transformation

Suppose that a particle is at rest in an inertial system S ($dx = 0$), and is moving with a velocity v with respect to an inertial system S' ($\frac{dx'^i}{dt'} = v^i$), From the transformation

$$dx' = \Lambda dx$$

or

$$dx'^{\mu} = \Lambda^{\mu}{}_{\nu} dx^{\nu}$$

it is obtained

$$dt' = \Lambda^0{}_0 dt \text{ and } dx'^i = \Lambda^i{}_0 c dt$$

and so

$$\Lambda^i{}_0 = \frac{v^i}{c} \Lambda^0{}_0$$

From the condition $\Lambda \eta \Lambda^T = \eta$, the following equation is obtained

$$-(\Lambda^0{}_0)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 (\Lambda^i{}_0)^2 = -1$$

The solution to these two last equations is

$$\Lambda^0{}_0 = \gamma$$

$$\Lambda^i{}_0 = -\gamma \frac{v^i}{c}$$

From the same condition, there is also

$$-(\Lambda^0{}_j)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 (\Lambda^i{}_j)^2 = 1$$

The solution to this equation is

$$\Lambda^0{}_j = -\gamma \frac{v_j}{c}$$

$$\Lambda^i{}_j = \delta_j^i + v^i v_j \frac{\gamma - 1}{v^2}$$

Therefore

$$\Lambda(v) = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & -\gamma \frac{v_x}{c} & -\gamma \frac{v_y}{c} & -\gamma \frac{v_z}{c} \\ -\gamma \frac{v_x}{c} & 1 + \frac{v_x^2 (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} & \frac{v_x v_y (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} & \frac{v_x v_z (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} \\ -\gamma \frac{v_y}{c} & \frac{v_x v_y (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} & 1 + \frac{v_y^2 (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} & \frac{v_y v_z (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} \\ -\gamma \frac{v_z}{c} & \frac{v_z v_x (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} & \frac{v_z v_y (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} & 1 + \frac{v_z^2 (\gamma - 1)}{v^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Any general Lorentz transformation is of the form $\Lambda = \Lambda(v)R$, where R is an arbitrary rotation of three spatial axes.

1.7 Lorentz and Poincaré generators and Lie algebras

1.7.1 Generators

i/ Using vector field picture : If the basis of the Poincaré algebra is :

$M_{\mu\nu} = x_{\mu} \partial_{\nu} - x_{\nu} \partial_{\mu}$: which are the six Lorentz generators where M_{ij} are the rotation

generators ($M_{ij} = x_i \partial_j - x_j \partial_i$) and M_{0i} are the boost generators ($M_{0i} = x_0 \partial_i - x_i \partial_0$) and $P_\mu = \partial_\mu$ are the four translation generators.

by exponentiation, we get the following flow

$$\exp\left(\frac{\theta^{\mu\nu}}{2} M_{\mu\nu} + a^\mu P_\mu\right)x = \Lambda x + a$$

where Λ is the general proper-orthochronous Lorentz matrix and the components of a are translation parameters which form together an element of the Poincaré group (or the special Poincaré group because here $\Lambda \in SO^\uparrow(3, 1)$; space and time reflections cannot be obtained by exponentiation).

ii/ Using infinitesimal generators :

In field theory, the objects that we are dealing with are fields which are functions of spacetime events. For instance, the simplest example would be the scalar field which transform as : $\phi'(x) = \phi(\Lambda^{-1}x - a) = [\exp - (\frac{\theta^{\mu\nu}}{2} M_{\mu\nu} + a^\mu P_\mu)]\phi(x)$ considering infinitesimal Poincaré transformation ($|\theta^{\mu\nu}| \ll 1, |a^\mu| \ll 1$), one finds the same generators expressions we found using the vector field picture.

$M_{\mu\nu}$ and P_μ are differential operators acting a space of functions ϕ which is an infinite-dimensional vector space, therefore they correspond to an infinite-dimensional representation of the Poincaré group.

Lorentz action on momentum space ¹

If one wants an expression of the Lorentz generators acting on momentum space rather than a space of functions ϕ , then the following substitutions in those generators are necessary:

$$P_\mu = \partial_\mu$$

$$x_\mu = -\frac{\partial}{\partial p^\mu}$$

Hence

$$M_{0i} = B_i = -cp_i \frac{\partial}{\partial E} - c^{-1}E \frac{\partial}{\partial p^i}$$

$$R^i = \frac{\epsilon^{ijk}}{2} M_{jk} = \epsilon^{ijk} p_j \frac{\partial}{\partial p^k}$$

the index "i" indicates that it is a boost in the ith direction or a rotation about the ith axis.

In the metric signature (+,-,-,-), they are expressed as

$$M_{0i} = B_i = cp_i \frac{\partial}{\partial E} + c^{-1}E \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i}$$

$$R^i = \frac{\epsilon^{ijk}}{2} M_{jk} = -\epsilon^{ijk} p_j \frac{\partial}{\partial p_k}$$

By using $P_\mu = \partial_\mu$, $x_\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial p^\mu}$

¹This paragraph is added for the sake of its extensive use in DSR program, in particular, the metric signature that will be adopted in DSR chapter is (+,-,-,-)

1.7.2 Poincaré and Lorentz algebras

Poincaré and Lorentz algebras are sets of -left invariant- fields that can be written as a linear combination of their basis, closed under the Lie bracket. The Lie bracket between the elements of the basis can be directly computed using the previous expressions of $M_{\mu\nu}$ and P_μ .

$$[M_{\mu\nu}, M_{\alpha\beta}] = \eta_{\mu\beta}M_{\nu\alpha} + \eta_{\nu\alpha}M_{\mu\beta} - \eta_{\mu\alpha}M_{\nu\beta} - \eta_{\nu\beta}M_{\mu\alpha}$$

$$[M_{\mu\nu}, P_\alpha] = \eta_{\nu\alpha}P_\mu - \eta_{\mu\alpha}P_\nu$$

$$[P_\alpha, P_\beta] = 0$$

Chapter 2

General relativity

2.1 Principles

General relativity (GR) was proposed by Einstein (1915), it is based on the following principles:

1. General relativity principle: All physical laws have the same forms in any coordinate system.
2. Equivalence principle: There exists a coordinate system where the effect of the gravitational field vanishes locally. (locally, the effects of uniform acceleration and gravity are equivalent.)

2.2 Spacetime of general relativity

Spacetime of GR is a generalization of Minkowski space to some 4-dimensional manifold M endowed with a pseudo-Riemannian metric g , which is a tensor field of type $(0, 2)$ satisfying the following properties:

Consider two tangent vectors U and V to M at a point x , the properties of g at each point $x \in M$ ($g(x) \equiv g_x$) are

- i/ $g_x(U, V) = g_x(V, U)$
- ii/ If $g_x(U, V) = 0 \quad \forall U$, then $V = 0$

Points in M are called *events*. Using a chart (U_i, Φ_i) , $x_i = (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3)$ and $g_x = g_{\mu\nu}(x)dx^\mu \otimes dx^\nu$. The index x in g_x is usually omitted .

The metric tensor field g is identified with the gravitational field, hence gravitation is a geometric theory governed by field equations, that will be derived later, with the 10 potentials $g_{\mu\nu}$ as solutions.

Indices are raised and lowered by means of g_x : There is an isomorphism $g_x(,)$ between $T_x M$ and $T_x^* M$, so that $V^\mu = g^{\mu\nu}V_\nu$ and $W_\mu = g_{\mu\nu}W^\nu$ with $g^{\alpha\gamma}g_{\gamma\beta} = \delta_\beta^\alpha$.

Taking an infinitesimal displacement $U = dx^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}$ and defining the invariant space-time interval,

$$ds^2 = g(U, U) = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu = g_{00} dt^2 + 2g_{0j} dt dx^j + g_{jk} dx^j dx^k$$

Tangent vectors are classified into three classes

- i/ $g(U, U) > 0 \rightarrow U$ is space-like
- ii/ $g(U, U) = 0 \rightarrow U$ is light-like
- iii/ $g(U, U) < 0 \rightarrow U$ is time-like

2.3 Linear connection

On a differentiable manifold, a linear connection is an extra structure that can be defined to allow the definition of a directional derivative of any tensor field of type (p,q) and to define the parallel transport.

Definition: a linear connection on a differentiable manifold M is a map,

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma : D(M) &\rightarrow \otimes_1^1 M \\ X &\rightarrow \nabla X \end{aligned}$$

Such that

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla(X + Y) &= \nabla X + \nabla Y \\ \nabla(fX) &= df \otimes X + f \nabla X \end{aligned}$$

where $X, Y \in D(M)$ denoting the set of vector fields on M and $f \in C(M)$, the set of differentiable functions on M. ∇X is called the covariant derivative of X.

The connection coefficients $\Gamma_{\nu\mu}^\lambda$ are defined by the following expression,

$$\nabla\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}\right) = \Gamma_{\nu\mu}^\lambda dx^\nu \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\lambda}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla X &= \nabla\left(X^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}\right) = dX^\mu \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} + X^\mu \nabla \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \\ &= (dX^\mu + X^\lambda \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu dx^\nu) \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial X^\mu}{\partial x^\nu} dx^\nu + X^\lambda \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu dx^\nu\right) \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial X^\mu}{\partial x^\nu} + X^\lambda \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu\right) dx^\nu \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} = X_{;\nu}^\mu dx^\nu \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \end{aligned}$$

$X_{;\nu}^\mu$ (or $\nabla_\nu X^\mu$) are the components of the tensor field ∇X .

∇X can be written in another form,

$$\nabla X = (dX^\mu + X^\lambda w_\lambda^\mu) \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}$$

where $w_{\nu\lambda}^{\mu} = \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^{\mu} dx^{\nu}$ are the connection forms.

The transformation law of the connection coefficients can be computed using the fact that ∇X is a tensor field of type (1,1),

$$\Gamma'_{\nu\lambda}{}^{\mu} = \frac{\partial x'^{\mu}}{\partial x^{\beta}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'^{\nu}} \left(\frac{\partial x^{\beta}}{\partial x'^{\lambda}} \right) + \frac{\partial x^{\beta}}{\partial x'^{\nu}} \frac{\partial x^{\gamma}}{\partial x'^{\lambda}} \frac{\partial x'^{\mu}}{\partial x^{\alpha}} \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha}$$

Parallel transport :

Covariant derivative of X in the direction of Y,

$$\nabla_Y X = (\nabla X)Y$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_Y X &= Y^{\nu} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\nu}} X^{\mu} + X^{\lambda} \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^{\mu} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\mu}} \\ &= (Y(X^{\mu}) + Y^{\nu} X^{\lambda} \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^{\mu}) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\mu}} \end{aligned}$$

A vector V is said to be parallel along a curve $x : \tau \rightarrow x(\tau)$, if $\nabla_U V = 0$, $U^{\mu} = \frac{dx^{\mu}(\tau)}{d\tau}$.

Geodesic: A geodesic on M is a curve $x : \tau \rightarrow x(\tau)$ such that $\nabla_U U = 0$, $U^{\mu} = \frac{dx^{\mu}(\tau)}{d\tau}$

In components, the equation $\nabla_U U = 0$ reads,

$$\frac{d^2 x^{\mu}(\tau)}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^{\mu} \frac{dx^{\nu}}{d\tau} \frac{dx^{\lambda}}{d\tau} = 0$$

In order to extend the covariant derivative to tensor fields of any type, the following requirements are added,

- 1/ $\nabla_X f = X[f]$ $f \in C(M)$
- 2/ $\nabla_X(t + s) = \nabla_X t + \nabla_X s$
- 3/ $\nabla_X(t \otimes s) = \nabla_X t \otimes s + t \otimes \nabla_X s$
- 4/ $[\nabla_X, C] = 0$, C is the contraction operation

Since the connection does not have an intrinsic meaning but rather depends on the choice of coordinate systems, the following operations are defined

Torsion and curvature operations τ and ρ :

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(X, Y) &= \nabla_X Y - \nabla_Y X - [X, Y] \\ \rho(X, Y) &= \nabla_X \nabla_Y - \nabla_Y \nabla_X - \nabla_{[X, Y]} \end{aligned}$$

Torsion and curvature tensor fields T and R :

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha, X, Y) &= \alpha(\tau(X, Y)) \\ R(\beta, \alpha, X, Y) &= \alpha(\rho(X, Y)\beta) \end{aligned}$$

$\alpha \in \Lambda^1(M)$ which denotes the set of one-forms on M and $\beta, X, Y \in D(M)$

Torsion and curvature tensor components :

$$T^\mu{}_{\nu\lambda} = T(dx^\mu, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\lambda}) = \Gamma^\mu_{\nu\lambda} - \Gamma^\mu_{\lambda\nu}$$

$$R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\lambda\sigma} = R(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}, dx^\nu, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\lambda}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\sigma}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\lambda} \Gamma^\nu_{\sigma\mu} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\sigma} \Gamma^\nu_{\lambda\mu} + \Gamma^\gamma_{\sigma\mu} \Gamma^\nu_{\lambda\gamma} - \Gamma^\gamma_{\lambda\mu} \Gamma^\nu_{\sigma\gamma}$$

2.4 Riemannian connection

In a (pseudo-) Riemannian manifold (M, g) , there is a unique linear connection such that

$$1/T = 0$$

$$2/\nabla g = 0$$

By combining the following equations,

$$\Gamma^\mu_{\nu\lambda} - \Gamma^\mu_{\lambda\nu} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x^\alpha} g_{\mu\nu} = \Gamma^\beta_{\alpha\mu} g_{\beta\nu} + \Gamma^\beta_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}$$

it results that the coefficients of Riemann connection are:

$$\Gamma^\gamma_{\alpha\mu} = \frac{1}{2} g^{\gamma\nu} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^\alpha} g_{\mu\nu} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} g_{\nu\alpha} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} g_{\alpha\mu} \right)$$

Properties of Riemann tensor :

$$1/ R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\lambda\sigma} = -R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\sigma\lambda}$$

$$2/ R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\lambda\sigma} + R_{\sigma}{}^{\nu}{}_{\mu\lambda} + R_{\lambda}{}^{\nu}{}_{\sigma\mu} = 0 \text{ 1st Bianchi identity}$$

$$3/ \nabla_\alpha R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\lambda\sigma} + \nabla_\sigma R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\alpha\lambda} + \nabla_\lambda R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\sigma\alpha} = 0 \text{ 2nd Bianchi identity}$$

$$4/ R_{\mu\nu\lambda\sigma} = -R_{\nu\mu\lambda\sigma}$$

$$5/ R_{\mu\nu\lambda\sigma} = R_{\lambda\sigma\mu\nu}$$

Ricci tensor:

$$R_{\mu\sigma} := R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\nu\sigma}$$

property : $R_{\mu\sigma} = R_{\sigma\mu}$ (using 1st Bianchi identity , 1st property of Riemann tensor and then contracting).

$$R_{\mu\sigma} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} \Gamma^\nu_{\sigma\mu} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\sigma} \Gamma^\nu_{\nu\mu} + \Gamma^\gamma_{\sigma\mu} \Gamma^\nu_{\nu\gamma} - \Gamma^\gamma_{\nu\mu} \Gamma^\nu_{\sigma\gamma}$$

Riemann curvature scalar:

$$\mathcal{R} = g^{\mu\sigma} R_{\mu\sigma}$$

Contraction of the 2nd Bianchi identity (ν, λ) gives

$$\nabla_\alpha R_{\mu\sigma} - \nabla_\sigma R_{\mu\alpha} + \nabla_\nu R_{\mu}{}^{\nu}{}_{\sigma\alpha} = 0$$

multiplying by $g^{\mu\alpha}$

$$\nabla_\alpha (R^\alpha{}_\sigma - \frac{1}{2}\delta_\sigma^\alpha \mathcal{R}) = 0$$

raising the σ index

$$\nabla_\alpha (R^{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\alpha\beta}\mathcal{R}) = 0$$

$$\nabla_\alpha G^{\alpha\beta} = 0$$

where $G^{\alpha\beta} := R^{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\alpha\beta}\mathcal{R}$ is called the Einstein tensor.

The contemplation of equating (apart from a constant) $G^{\alpha\beta}$ to $T^{\alpha\beta}$, the energy-momentum tensor of matter, since they both satisfy the covariant conservation equation, is true because it can be derived by variation using the action principle.

One thing to emphasize is that GR principles imply a curved spacetime since, mathematically, there exists a coordinate frame where the metric at a point x reduces, locally, to Minkowski metric (local flatness theorem). On the other hand, the identification of the gravitational field with the metric tensor field g was furthermore justified by noticing that in the weak field limit, g_{00} is closely related to Newton's gravitational potential, so the other $g_{\mu\nu}$ must also play a role:

Assumptions

- static metric $g_{00} = g_{00}(\mathbf{x})$, $g_{0i} = 0$, $g_{\alpha\beta} = g_{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{x})$ do not depend on time
- Consider a particle moving in a region where the gravitational field is weak, so it is approximately Minkowskian $g_{00} \approx -1 + h_{00}(\mathbf{x})$
- A freely falling particle moves along a geodesic in the spacetime manifold (M, g) .¹

From these, it results : $\frac{d^2x^k}{dt^2} \approx (\text{grad}(\frac{g_{00}}{2}))^k$

so that $g_{00} = -2\phi + \text{constant}$, where ϕ is the Newton's gravitational potential, at infinity this later vanishes, thus $g_{00} = -2\phi - 1$

¹In Newtonian mechanics, a free particle is a particle that is not subject to any forces, it moves along a geodesic. In GR, a free particle is a freely falling particle as long as gravity here is understood to be a part of spacetime geometry. By generalization, a freely falling particle is assumed to move along a geodesic in spacetime manifold.

2.5 Einstein's field equations

In order to see how the gravitational field evolves physically in spacetime manifold, the action principle is applied:

Einstein-Hilbert action

$$S_{EH} := \frac{1}{16\pi G} \int \mathcal{R} \sqrt{-\mathbf{g}} d^4x$$

The constant factor is chosen to reproduce the Newtonian limit and \mathbf{g} denotes the determinant of the metric.

$$\delta S_{EH} = \frac{1}{16\pi G} \int (-R^{\alpha\beta} + \frac{1}{2}g^{\alpha\beta}\mathcal{R})\delta g_{\alpha\beta}\sqrt{-\mathbf{g}}d^4x$$

Vacuum Einstein equations : $R^{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\alpha\beta}\mathcal{R} = 0$

In the existence of matter, the variation of matter action is given by

$$\delta S_M = \frac{1}{2} \int T^{\mu\nu} \delta g_{\mu\nu} \sqrt{-\mathbf{g}} d^4x$$

If gravitational field is coupled with matter, then the action principle reads

$$\delta(S_{EH} + S_M) = 0$$

which implies

$$G_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}$$

Newtonian limit:

- static metric
 $g_{00} = -2\phi - 1, g_{0i} = 0, g_{ij} = \delta_{ij}$
- $T_{00} = \rho, T_{0i} = T_{ij} = 0$

ρ is the matter density, Einstein field equations reduce to Poisson equation of Newton theory

$$\Delta\phi = 4\pi G\rho$$

Remark An extra scalar called the **cosmological constant**¹ may be added to Einstein equations without altering the null-divergence, symmetry and covariance or altering the invariance of the action

$$S_{EH}^* := \frac{1}{16\pi G} \int (\mathcal{R} - 2\Lambda)\sqrt{-\mathbf{g}}d^4x$$

¹originally introduced by Einstein for allowing a static universe ($\dot{a}, \ddot{a} = 0$, see Friedmann equations p19), then abandoned after the discovery of the expansion of the universe and finally reintroduced after the discovery of the acceleration of the universe's expansion and interpreted in terms of "vacuum energy".

$$G_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi GT_{\mu\nu}$$

Λ is assumed to be very small in order for general relativity to not deviate from Newton's theory of gravitation in the weak field limit.

2.6 Solutions

Since Einstein's equations are nonlinear differential equations of the second order, it is difficult to find exact solutions. However, there are two simplest cases for which these equations can be easily solved :

2.6.1 Schwarzschild metric

Consider a static spherically symmetric gravitational field produced by a spherically symmetric body of mass M at rest in an empty region , so that $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$.

The metric should have the form,

$$ds^2 = -e^{\nu(r)}dt^2 + e^{\lambda(r)}dr^2 + r^2d\theta^2 + r^2\sin^2\theta d\phi^2$$

ν and λ are arbitrary functions of r . In order to find the exact expression of the metric, Ricci tensor components are computed and imposed to vanish.

The non-vanishing connection coefficients are:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{10}^0 &= \frac{\nu'}{2} & \Gamma_{33}^1 &= -e^{-\lambda}r\sin^2\theta \\ \Gamma_{00}^1 &= \frac{\nu'}{2}e^{\nu-\lambda} & \Gamma_{12}^2 &= \Gamma_{13}^3 = \frac{1}{r} \\ \Gamma_{11}^1 &= \frac{\lambda'}{2} & \Gamma_{23}^3 &= \cot\theta \\ \Gamma_{22}^1 &= -e^{-\lambda}r & \Gamma_{33}^2 &= -\sin\theta\cos\theta \end{aligned}$$

The non-vanishing Ricci components are:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{00} &= \left(\frac{\nu''}{2} + \frac{(\nu')^2}{4} + \frac{\nu'}{r} - \frac{\nu'\lambda'}{4}\right)e^{\nu-\lambda} \\ R_{11} &= -\frac{\nu''}{2} + \frac{\nu'\lambda'}{4} + \frac{\lambda'}{r} - \frac{(\nu')^2}{4} \\ R_{22} &= \left(\frac{r\lambda'}{2} - 1 - \frac{r\nu'}{2}\right)e^{-\lambda} + 1 \\ R_{33} &= e^{-\lambda}\left(\frac{\nu'}{2}r\sin^2\theta - \frac{\lambda'}{2}r\sin^2\theta - \sin^2\theta\right) + \sin^2\theta \end{aligned}$$

The prime denotes a derivation with respect to r . Combining the equations $R_{00} = 0$ and $R_{11} = 0$ gives $\nu' + \lambda' = 0$ or $\nu + \lambda = cst$, at $r \rightarrow \infty$ both ν and λ tend to 0, thus $\nu + \lambda = 0$.

$R_{22} = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} (re^\nu)' &= 1 \\ e^\nu &= 1 + \frac{cst}{r} \\ r \rightarrow \infty \quad g_{00} &\approx \frac{2GM}{r} - 1 \Rightarrow cst = -2GM \end{aligned}$$

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{r}\right)dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{r}} + r^2d\theta^2 + r^2\sin^2\theta d\phi^2$$

Known as **Schwarzschild metric**, it describes the spacetime of a spherical body of mass M such as stars, it could be the sun, for which the singularity present in the metric is irrelevant since its radius is much larger than the Schwarzschild radius ($r_s = 2GM$), or objects such as black holes for which the singularity ($r = r_s$) becomes then relevant.

2.6.2 Friedmann-Robertson-Walker (FRW) metric

FRW metric is a cosmological model describing a non-static spatially homogenous and isotropic universe, such a spacetime is of the form $\mathbb{R} \times X$, where \mathbb{R} is the time direction and X is a three-dimensional homogenous and isotropic manifold. Thus the metric can be written in the form,

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a^2(t)\gamma_{ij}(x)dx^i dx^j$$

t is the time coordinate, x^i are coordinates of a point $x \in X$, γ is the metric on the manifold X and $a(t)$ is the scale factor which basically tells how big is X at an instant t .

The main interest is to determine the behavior of the scale factor using Einstein equations, but first, the form of the metric γ is examined:

Since a homogenous isotropic manifold is a maximally symmetric space¹, the metric obey to,

$$R_{ijkl}^{(X)} = k(\gamma_{ik}\gamma_{jl} - \gamma_{il}\gamma_{jk})$$

$$R_{jl}^{(X)} = 2k\gamma_{jl}$$

The exponent (X) indicates that it is Riemann and Ricci tensor corresponding to the space X and not to the whole spacetime and k is some constant. Considering that X is maximally symmetric, it has a spherical symmetry, thus

$$d\alpha^2 = \gamma_{ij}dx^i dx^j = e^\lambda dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)$$

It results that the FRW metric takes the form

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a^2(t)\left(\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)\right)$$

Three cases are of interest: $k=-1$ corresponds to constant negative curvature on X and is called open, $k=0$ corresponding to a null curvature, and is called flat and $k=1$ corresponding to a constant positive curvature, and is called closed.

The non-vanishing connection coefficients are :

$$\begin{array}{ll} \Gamma_{11}^0 = \frac{a\dot{a}}{1-kr^2} & \Gamma_{21}^2 = \Gamma_{33}^3 = \frac{1}{r} \\ \Gamma_{22}^0 = a\dot{a}r^2 & \Gamma_{33}^2 = -\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ \Gamma_{33}^0 = a\dot{a}r^2\sin^2\theta & \Gamma_{32}^3 = \cot\theta \\ \Gamma_{01}^1 = \Gamma_{02}^2 = \Gamma_{03}^3 = \frac{\dot{a}}{a} & \Gamma_{33}^1 = -(1 - kr^2)r\sin\theta \end{array}$$

¹An n -dimensional maximally symmetric space is a manifold that has $\frac{1}{2}n(n+1)$ Killing vector fields. A Killing vector field K is a vector field which generates an isometry, $\mathcal{L}_K g = 0$ where \mathcal{L}_K is the Lie derivative.

$$\Gamma_{22}^1 = -r(1 - kr^2)$$

The non-vanishing Ricci components are :

$$\begin{aligned} R_{00} &= -\frac{3\ddot{a}}{a} \\ R_{11} &= \frac{a\ddot{a} + 2\dot{a}^2 + 2k}{1 - kr^2} \\ R_{22} &= r^2(a\ddot{a} + 2\dot{a}^2 + 2k) \\ R_{33} &= (a\ddot{a} + 2\dot{a}^2 + 2k)r^2 \sin^2\theta \end{aligned}$$

Matter and energy in the universe are modeled by a perfect fluid,

$$T_{\mu\nu} = (p + \rho)U_\mu U_\nu + pg_{\mu\nu}$$

Where p is the pressure, ρ is energy density and U is the fluid's velocity four-vector $U = (1, 0, 0, 0)$

Recall that Einstein equations can be written in this form $R_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi G(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}T)$ where $T = g^{\alpha\beta}T_{\alpha\beta}$, as a consequence

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{3\ddot{a}}{a} &= 4\pi G(\rho + 3p) \\ \frac{\ddot{a}}{a} + \frac{2\dot{a}^2}{a^2} + \frac{2k}{a^2} &= 4\pi G(\rho - p) \end{aligned}$$

Using the first equation to rearrange the second one,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\ddot{a}}{a} &= -\frac{4\pi}{3}G(\rho + 3p) \\ \frac{\dot{a}^2}{a^2} &= \frac{8\pi G\rho}{3} - \frac{k}{a^2} \end{aligned}$$

These two equations are known as **Friedmann equations**.

In the presence of the cosmological constant, they take the form below

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\ddot{a}}{a} &= -\frac{4\pi}{3}G(\rho + 3p) + \frac{\Lambda}{3} \\ \frac{\dot{a}^2}{a^2} &= \frac{8\pi G\rho}{3} - \frac{k}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3} \end{aligned}$$

Chapter 3

Doubly Special Relativity

3.1 Introduction

The motivation behind the proposal of a relativity theory with two observer-independent scales rather than only one as in SR, has its roots from a conceptual aspect mainly but not only, some observations appear to disagree with SR predictions. These shall be presented as follows:

- In quantum-gravity research, when combining fundamental constants of the very familiar physical theories: special relativity (the speed of light c), general relativity (gravitational constant G) and quantum mechanics (quantum action or Planck's constant \hbar), one leads to the Planck length $l_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}$ or its inverse the Planck energy $E_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G}} = \hbar c l_p^{-1}$ ¹, about $10^{-35}m$ and $10^{19}GeV$ respectively. These are considered as scales which indicate thresholds beyond which quantum gravity phenomena are expected to appear. This length is around twenty orders of magnitude smaller than the nucleus size and this energy is far beyond what is attainable in particle accelerators, around sixteen orders of magnitude larger. Hence, at the present day, physics is not well defined experimentally at this specific scale, this creates anticipating challenges for the future of physics experiments.

What is often assumed is that this length should be attributed a role in short-distant structure of space-time, and if nature turns out to work this way, then a conflict arises conceptually: in contrast of assuming that l_p is an invariant physical length, it is learned from SR that physical lengths are in fact contracted from one observer to another. Therefore, it seems impossible to attribute an intrinsic (observer-independent) property to this length in the microscopic structure of space-time without modifying the postulates of special relativity.

Furthermore, in loop quantum gravity, there is a prediction of modified dispersion relations at Planck scales, usually of the form $E^2 = c^2 p^2 + m^2 c^4 + \xi L_p^n p^2 E^n + O(L_p^{n+1} E^{n+3})$, which may, in turn, predict an energy dependent speed of light. Such corrections to the SR dispersion relation are also shared by some experimental developments to be discussed in the following paragraph.

¹In what follows, these two quantities among other derived Planck quantities such as Planck momentum, Planck mass and Planck time will be used interchangeably.

- From a phenomenological point of view, there are some astrophysics observations [1] [2] of two kind of events that are in disagreement with SR predictions
 1. Ultra-High-Energy Cosmic Rays event: UHECR are particles identified as protons, produced from distant galaxies. During their journey, they interact with soft photons in the environment (left in the universe from its early stages of evolution, such as the Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation) following one of these process $p\gamma \rightarrow p\pi^0/p\gamma \rightarrow n + \pi^+$. Such a process is allowed only at an appropriate high energy, the threshold energy E_{th} (or E_{GZK} , GZK stands for Greisen–Zatsepin–Kuzmin for explaining the cut-off of UHECR by calculating the threshold of these reactions). Below this threshold, this process could not occur.
 2. Gamma-ray event: photons from the MK501 blazar, when having an appropriate high energy E_{th} , interact with soft photons in the environment, in particular the CMBR, following this process $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow e^-e^+$.

The values of these thresholds are obtained theoretically using the energy-momentum conservation law and the dispersion relation just as shown in the appendix. These are around $10^{20}eV$ for the UHECR and 10^8eV for the gamma-ray reaction.

What is expected is that UHECR and γ -Ray particles having energies beyond these limits could not reach the earth because then, it would be possible for the processes above to occur, creating pairs of other particles. In other words, a cut-off of these UHECR and γ - Ray particles is expected beyond these thresholds, serving as boundaries from continuing their travel.

However, anomalies appear: from observations made by Akeno Giant Air Shower Array (AGASA), there are UHECR protons and possibly also MK501-photons, with energies beyond the thresholds predicted by SR, that reach the earth.

The experimental situation is still controversial according to High Resolution Fly's Eye Experiment (HiRes) and Pierre Auger Observatory. Meanwhile, waiting an objective confirmation of these interesting experimental results that could open windows to new physics, Amelino-Camelia followed by other researchers to name few of them Smolin, Magueijo, Kowalski-Glikman... took advantage of the situation as a motivation for developing theoretical ideas that could match with what quantum-gravity research happens to suggest and at the same time resolve these paradoxes, that is, these cosmic-ray and γ -ray anomalies may be explained by the fact that SR dispersion relation is modified at Planck scale.

Now, for l_p to be incorporated in physics and for the SR dispersion relation to be modified at Planck scale in order to solve the conflict of quantum-gravity studies with SR and solve the thresholds anomalies, many questions arise at the first attempt of constructing a theory which include these hypotheses, three questions seem to be

relevant for the authors mentioned above: (a) are there different directions to take to construct such a theory? (b) how would it be constructed in each direction? and (c) how this theory could be tested/falsifiable ?

(a) It is suggested that two directions are possible:

- 1 Relativistic short-distance structure of spacetime : It does not violate the relativity principle. SR postulates will be modified in a way that l_p becomes a second observer-independent quantity, in addition to the speed of light, making the relativity theory doubly special so that all observers will agree on the scale beyond which quantum-gravity effects are supposed to appear and this leads to a modified dispersion relation, knowing that SR formulas should be recovered at large distances or low energies.
- 2 Non-relativistic short-distance structure of spacetime : it violates the relativity principle, there is a preferred frame in nature where l_p is considered as a threshold for quantum-gravity phenomena and in which the SR dispersion relation takes a different form at this scale.

(b) 1 For the relativistic theory, this is constructed based on a deformation of the boost generator, which leaves the modified dispersion relation invariant. But here again, there is two different methods for performing such a deformation:

- i Deformation of the boost generator acting on momentum space, defined to be non linear in order for l_p to be invariant.
- ii Quantum deformation of the boost generator, which yields a quantum Lorentz group.

The authors believe that a deformation of the boost generator acting on momentum space is a better candidate for constructing DSR than a quantum deformation would do, this is based on the following argument: from a physical point of view, the transformations between observers must verify the axioms of a group, in particular the inverse property should be satisfied. This axiom is weakened in quantum groups.

- 2 A non-relativistic theory would be built upon breaking the Lorentz symmetry. This is not treated in the thesis.

(c) There are many ways to test DSR, but the first evidence is that any observation of Lorentz-breaking symmetry would completely exclude DSR. Whether Lorentz symmetry is broken or modified, this could be observed, in near future, in two classes of experiments leading to a better awareness of l_p role:

- Experiments in which Planck scale corrections to the energy-momentum relations are observable, e.g. cosmic ray spectra and gamma ray bursts.

- Experiments in which an energy dependent speed of light is observable, e.g. AMS (Alpha Magnetic Spectrometer) and GLAST (Gamma-ray Large Area Space Telescope).

3.2 DSR1

3.2.1 Postulates

DSR1 is proposed by Amelino-Camelia [3] [4] [5] [6], it is based on the following postulates:

1. Relativity principle : All physical laws have the same forms in any inertial system.
2. The speed of light c is an observer-independent scale for the limit $\frac{\lambda}{L_{dsr}} \rightarrow \infty$ (λ is the light wavelength) ¹.
3. L_{dsr} is an observer-independent length scale, possibly Planckian, measured by determining the dispersion relation for photons taking the form,

$$E^2 - c^2 p^2 + f(E, p, L_{dsr}) = 0 \quad (3.2.1)$$

where f is invariant in all inertial systems. At L_{dsr} leading order it is given by $f(E, p, L_{dsr}) \simeq -L_{dsr} c p^2 E$.

3.2.2 DSR1 model

At first, a leading-order example will be given, then this will be extrapolated to an all-order function f .

i *Leading-order f*

Dispersion relation :

DSR theories are characterized, conceptually and phenomenologically, by deformed dispersion relations. For the case of DSR1 leading-order correction, which is meaningful for experimental searches, it has the form bellow

For photons:

$$E^2 - c^2 p^2 - L_{dsr} c p^2 E = 0 \quad (3.2.2)$$

For massive particles:

$$E^2 - c^2 p^2 - m^2 c^4 - L_{dsr} c p^2 E = 0 \quad (3.2.3)$$

¹the speed of light is still considered as an observer-independent quantity but with a little carefullness when dealing with energies comparable to the Planck energy, its status should not be naively extrapolated from SR to DSR.

Boost generator:

Since the above dispersion relation is invariant under rotation but not invariant under boost, the rotation generator is left unchanged and the SR boost generator is modified (see appendix for any DSR1/DSR2 detailed calculations).

$$R^i = \frac{\epsilon^{ijk}}{2} M_{jk} = -\epsilon^{ijk} p_j \frac{\partial}{\partial p_k} \quad (3.2.4)$$

$$B_i = cp_i \frac{\partial}{\partial E} + c^{-1} E \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} - L_{dsr} E^2 c^{-2} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} + L_{dsr} \frac{p^2}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} - L_{dsr} p_i (p_k \frac{\partial}{\partial p_k}) \quad (3.2.5)$$

Although the boost generator is modified, the Lorentz algebra is unchanged as it can be checked

$$[R^i, R^j] = \epsilon^{ijk} R_k, \quad [B^i, B^j] = -\epsilon^{ijk} R_k, \quad [R^i, B^j] = -\epsilon^{ijk} B_k$$

Finite modified Lorentz transformations (acting on momentum space):

In order to find the finite modified Lorentz transformation acting on momentum space, one must solve the following differential equations:

$$\frac{dE(\phi)}{d\phi} = [B_i, E] = cp_i(\phi) \quad (3.2.6)$$

$$\frac{dp_i(\phi)}{d\phi} = [B_i, p_i] = E(\phi)c^{-1} - L_{dsr} E^2(\phi)c^{-2} - L_{dsr} \frac{p^2(\phi)}{2} \quad (3.2.7)$$

Where ϕ is the transformation parameter (rapidity).

If $L_{dsr} \rightarrow 0$, the ordinary differential equations corresponding to Lorentz transformation on momentum space, SR boost generator and dispersion relation are recovered.

Energy-momentum conservation laws:

Because of the structure of the transformation rules (3.2.6) and (3.2.7), SR laws of energy-momentum conservation are no longer invariant. So these should be modified as well, for a reaction $ab \rightarrow cd$:

$$E_a + E_b - L_{dsr} cp_a p_b - E_c - E_d + L_{dsr} cp_c p_d = 0 \quad (3.2.8)$$

$$p_a + p_b - L_{dsr} c^{-1} (E_a p_b + E_b p_a) - p_c - p_d + L_{dsr} c^{-1} (E_c p_d + E_d p_c) = 0 \quad (3.2.9)$$

As noticed in [3] [4] [5], this process of modifying the conservation rules, which is directly associated with the introduction of an observer-independent scale L_{dsr} , is analogous to the modification of Galilean velocity composition law which was associated with the the introduction of the speed of light

as an observer-independent scale. Hence, to each process of laws modification in these relativistic theories (Galilean, SR) corresponds a new observer-independent scale. Note also that if $L_{dsr} \rightarrow 0$, the SR conservation rules are recovered.

The invariance of the new conservation laws can be checked by using equations (3.2.6) (3.2.7),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\phi}(E_a + E_b - L_{dsr}cp_ap_b - E_c - E_d + L_{dsr}cp_cp_d) = & -c(p_a + p_b - L_{dsr}c^{-1}(E_ap_b \\ & + E_bp_a) - p_c - p_d + L_{dsr}c^{-1}(E_cp_d + E_dp_c)) \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\phi}(p_a + p_b - L_{dsr}c^{-1}(E_ap_b + E_bp_a) - p_c - p_d + L_{dsr}c^{-1}(E_cp_d + E_dp_c)) = \\ -c^{-1}(E_a + E_b - L_{dsr}cp_ap_b - E_c - E_d + L_{dsr}cp_cp_d) \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.11)$$

This example is useful and sufficient for possible experimental tests of DSR1 which will be sensitive only to leading-order effects, but for the logical consistency of the theory, it is necessary to verify that other all-order functions can be adopted.

ii *All-order* f^1

One possible choice for the function f is :

$$f(E, p, L_{dsr}) = \frac{2}{L_{dsr}^2}(\cosh(L_{dsr}E) - 1) - p^2 e^{L_{dsr}E} - E^2 + p^2 \quad (3.2.12)$$

Dispersion relation :

For photons:

$$\frac{2}{L_{dsr}^2}(\cosh(L_{dsr}E) - 1) = p^2 e^{L_{dsr}E} \quad (3.2.13)$$

For massive particles

$$\frac{2}{L_{dsr}^2}(\cosh(L_{dsr}E) - 1) - p^2 e^{L_{dsr}E} = m^2 \quad (3.2.14)$$

The dispersion relation is reduced to (3.2.2) when approximated in leading order.

¹In what follows $c=1$ unless it is highlighted in a certain equation on purpose.

Boost generator :

$$B_i = p_i \frac{\partial}{\partial E} + \frac{L_{dsr}}{2} p^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} + \frac{1 - e^{-2L_{dsr}E}}{2L_{dsr}} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} - L_{dsr} p_i \left(p_k \frac{\partial}{\partial p_k} \right) \quad (3.2.15)$$

The boost generator is reduced to (3.2.5) when approximated in leading order. As in leading-order boost, it can be verified that the Lorentz algebra is unmodified.

Finite modified Lorentz transformations (acting on momentum space):

$$\frac{dE(\phi)}{d\phi} = [B_i, E] = p_i(\phi) \quad (3.2.16)$$

$$\frac{dp_i(\phi)}{d\phi} = [B_i, p_i] = -\frac{L_{dsr}}{2} p^2(\phi) + \frac{1 - e^{-2L_{dsr}E(\phi)}}{2L_{dsr}} \quad (3.2.17)$$

The solution to these equations is :

$$E(\phi) = E_0 + \frac{1}{L_{dsr}} \ln(1 + \sin(L_{dsr}M) e^{-L_{dsr}M} (\cosh\phi - 1)) \quad (3.2.18)$$

$$p_i(\phi) = \frac{1}{L_{dsr}} \frac{\sinh(L_{dsr}M) e^{-L_{dsr}M} \sinh\phi}{1 + \sinh(L_{dsr}M) e^{-L_{dsr}M} (\cosh\phi - 1)} \quad (3.2.19)$$

They satisfy

$$\frac{2}{L_{dsr}^2} (\cosh(L_{dsr}E(\phi)) - 1) = p^2(\phi) e^{-L_{dsr}E(\phi)} + m^2$$

Energy-momentum conservation laws :

Judes and Visser [11] found exact conservation rules for both DSR1 and DSR2 by introducing auxiliary energy-momentum, the derivation is found in the appendix

$$\frac{1}{L_{dsr}} \ln \left[L_{dsr} \epsilon^{tot} \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4} ((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)} + 1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{2} ((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2) \right] = 0 \quad (3.2.20)$$

$$\frac{\pi^{tot} \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4} ((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)}}{L_{dsr} \epsilon^{tot} \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4} ((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)} + 1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{2} ((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)} = 0 \quad (3.2.21)$$

with

$$\epsilon^{tot} = \sum_i \frac{e^{L_{dsr}E_i} - \cosh(L_{dsr}M_{,i})}{L_{dsr} \cosh(L_{dsr}M_{,i}/2)}$$

$$\pi^{tot} = \sum_i \frac{p_i e^{L_{dsr}E_i}}{\cosh(L_{dsr}M_{,i}/2)}$$

3.2.3 Predictions

i Energy dependent speed of light :

If the speed-of-light law $v_\gamma = \frac{dE}{dp}$ holds in DSR theory, then DSR1 predicts an energy dependent speed of light,

$$v_\gamma \approx c\left(1 + \frac{L_{dsr}}{2}c^{-1}E\right) \quad (3.2.22)$$

ii Threshold anomalies :

By combining (3.2.8), (3.2.9) and (3.2.3), it turns out that DSR1 predicts very small corrections to the SR thresholds for both UHECR and gamma-ray, these corrections are of the order $L_{dsr}E_{th}^2$ which is below the experimental sensitivity.

3.3 DSR2

3.3.1 Postulates

In the paper where DSR2 has been proposed [9], Smolin and Magueijo proposed, intuitively, that a combination of the ordinary boost generator with the dilatation generator could be an interesting one for fixing the Planck energy scale when acting on momentum space. It has to be a non-linear action on momentum space since it is known that the ordinary linear action does not fix any energy scale. Moreover, the combination must be done by incorporating the Planck energy in a certain way which carefully ensures its invariance as it has already pointed out in the introduction of this chapter.

3.3.2 DSR2 model

Dispersion relation :

As in DSR1, a key characteristic of DSR2 is the deformed dispersion relation

$$\frac{E^2}{(1 - L_{dsr}E)^2} - \frac{c^2p^2}{(1 - L_{dsr}E)^2} = m^2 \quad (3.3.1)$$

For photons, the dispersion relation is not modified $E^2 - c^2p^2 = 0$.

Boost generator:

The above dispersion relation is invariant under the following boost generator,

$$B_i = B_i^{SR} + L_{dsr}p_i D \quad (3.3.2)$$

Where $D = p_\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial p_\mu}$ is the dilatation generator ¹ and B_i^{SR} is the ordinary boost of special relativity.

This modified boost does not modify the Lorentz algebra.

Finite modified Lorentz transformation (acting on momentum space):

DSR2 boost generator may be re-written in this form,

$$B_i = U^{-1} B_i^{SR} U \quad (3.3.3)$$

Where

$$U \equiv e^{L_{dsr}p_0 D} \quad (3.3.4)$$

$$U^{-1} \equiv e^{-L_{dsr}p_0 D} \quad (3.3.5)$$

The nonlinear representation of the Lorentz group on momentum space is then,

$$D[\Lambda] = U^{-1} e^{\theta^{\mu\nu} M_{\mu\nu}^{SR}} U \quad (3.3.6)$$

¹defined by $D := x_\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu}$, the dilatation generator is one of the generators of conformal symmetry.

Therefore the boost in x direction is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
p'_0 &= \frac{\gamma(p_0 - vp_x)}{1 + L_{dsr}(\gamma - 1)p_0 - L_{dsr}\gamma vp_x} \\
p'_x &= \frac{\gamma(p_x - vp_0)}{1 + L_{dsr}(\gamma - 1)p_0 - L_{dsr}\gamma vp_x} \\
p'_y &= \frac{p_y}{1 + L_{dsr}(\gamma - 1)p_0 - L_{dsr}\gamma vp_y} \\
p'_z &= \frac{p_z}{1 + L_{dsr}(\gamma - 1)p_0 - L_{dsr}\gamma vp_z}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.7}$$

When $L_{dsr} \rightarrow 0$ (large distances or low energies), this transformation on momentum space reduces to the usual SR boost.

From this deformed transformation, $E_{dsr} = L_{dsr}^{-1}$ is invariant.

Energy momentum conservation rules:

Based on the work of Judes and Visser [11], the conservation rules are :

$$\frac{\sum_i \frac{E_i}{1 - L_{dsr} E_i}}{1 + L_{dsr} \sum_i \frac{E_i}{1 - L_{dsr} E_i}} = 0 \tag{3.3.8}$$

$$\frac{\sum_i \frac{P_i}{1 - L_{dsr} E_i}}{1 + L_{dsr} \sum_i \frac{P_i}{1 - L_{dsr} E_i}} = 0 \tag{3.3.9}$$

At leading order,

$$E_a + E_b - L_{dsr} E_a E_b - E_c - E_d + L_{dsr} E_c E_d = 0 \tag{3.3.10}$$

$$p_a + p_b - L_{dsr} p_a E_b - p_c - p_d + L_{dsr} p_c E_d = 0 \tag{3.3.11}$$

3.3.3 Predictions

i Energy dependent speed of light :

By assuming that the speed-of-light law is $v_\gamma = \frac{dE}{dp}$, it results that DSR2 does not predict an energy dependent speed of light $v_\gamma = c$.

ii Threshold anomalies: DSR2 does not predict large corrections to threshold reactions in order to be tested experimentally, by combining (3.3.10), (3.3.11) and (3.3.1) it turns out the corrections are of the order of $L_{dsr} E_{th}^2$.

3.4 De Sitter momentum space and DSR

After constructing DSR theory, the goal was to try to attach it to a certain mathematical framework, κ -Poincaré algebra was found to be an adequate algebraic approach. DSR1 and DSR2 are, in fact, representations of the same κ -Poincaré algebra in different bases where the Casimir of the algebra in each basis determines the dispersion relation of the model in question, this shows their equivalence. The interested reader is referred to the paper [13] for a detailed treatment of the relation between DSR models and κ -Poincaré algebra.

In this thesis, we give the second approach proposed by Glikman [14] [15], who realized that the De Sitter energy-momentum space could be a natural setting for DSR, based on the following argument: DSR symmetry is a ten parameter group consisting of translational symmetry whose generators are positions and Lorentz group nonlinearly realized on energy-momentum space, if this later is thought of as a four-dimensional manifold then this must be a maximally symmetric space, there are three cases: positive, null or negative constant curvature, each corresponding to De Sitter, flat or anti-De Sitter space. The reason why De Sitter was chosen is that DSR generators can form $so(4,1)$ algebra which is an algebra of symmetries of De Sitter space.

De sitter momentum space is a four-dimensional maximally symmetric space of positive constant curvature whose points are energies-momenta. It can be constructed as an embedding in a five-dimensional Minkowski space

$$ds^2 = -d\eta_0^2 + d\eta_1^2 + d\eta_2^2 + d\eta_3^2 + d\eta_4^2 \quad (3.4.1)$$

with

$$-\eta_0^2 + \eta_1^2 + \eta_2^2 + \eta_3^2 + \eta_4^2 = \kappa^2 \quad (3.4.2)$$

The metric is invariant under $SO(4,1)$ whose generators might be decomposed by Cartan decomposition¹ into rotations, boosts forming the sub-algebra $so(3,1)$ and the remaining generators X_μ called positions. The commutators are given by

$$[R^i, R^j] = \epsilon^{ijk} R_k, \quad [B^i, B^j] = -\epsilon^{ijk} R_k, \quad [R^i, B^j] = -\epsilon^{ijk} B_k \quad (3.4.3)$$

which is the usual Lorentz algebra and

$$[X_0, X_i] = -\frac{1}{\kappa^2} B_i, \quad [X_i, X_j] = \frac{1}{\kappa^2} \epsilon_{ijk} R_k \quad (3.4.4)$$

$$[B_i, X_0] = X_i, \quad [B_i, X_j] = \delta_{ij} X_0 \quad (3.4.5)$$

Where κ has the dimension L^{-1} , it is related to Planck mass. It is added in the commutators to rescale the X_μ generators so that they have dimension of length. Other decompositions are, of course, possible.

These generators act on the coordinates $\eta_0, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4$ as follows

¹Cartan decomposition is a vector space decomposition of a finite dimensional semi-simple algebra L : $L = K \oplus U$ where K and U satisfy the following commutation relations $[K, K] \subseteq K$, $[K, U] \subseteq U$ and $[U, U] \subseteq K$.

$$[X_0, \eta_4] = \frac{1}{\kappa} \eta_0, \quad [X_0, \eta_0] = \frac{1}{\kappa} \eta_4, \quad [X_0, \eta_i] = 0 \quad (3.4.6)$$

$$[X_i, \eta_4] = \frac{1}{\kappa} \eta_i, \quad [X_i, \eta_0] = 0, \quad [X_i, \eta_j] = -\frac{1}{\kappa} \delta_{ij} \eta_4 \quad (3.4.7)$$

$$[R_i, \eta_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} \eta_k, \quad [B_i, \eta_j] = \delta_{ij} \eta_0, \quad [B_i, \eta_0] = \eta_i \quad (3.4.8)$$

Each coordinate system built on the space (3.4.1) leads to some DSR theory, in particular, DSR1 can be recovered with the following coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_0 &= \kappa \sinh \frac{p_0}{\kappa} + \frac{p^2}{2\kappa} e^{\frac{p_0}{\kappa}} \\ \eta_i &= p_i e^{\frac{p_0}{\kappa}} \\ \eta_4 &= \kappa \cosh \frac{p_0}{\kappa} - \frac{p^2}{2\kappa} e^{\frac{p_0}{\kappa}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.9)$$

Using (3.4.8), (3.4.9) and Leibnitz rule, the commutator (3.2.17) is recovered.

For DSR2, the commutator of boost with p_j

$$[B_i, p_j] = \delta_{ij} p_0 + L_{dsr} p_i p_j \quad (3.4.10)$$

is recovered by using the following coordinates :

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_0 &= -\frac{p_0}{1 - \frac{p_0}{\kappa}} \\ \eta_i &= \frac{p_i}{1 - \frac{p_0}{\kappa}} \\ \eta_4 &= \sqrt{\kappa^2 + \eta_0^2 - \eta_2^2 - \eta_3^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.11)$$

3.5 Conclusion

The general schemes of the two DSR models resemble each other in the sense that they are both based on deformation of dispersion relation, involve deformation of conservation rules, constructed from a deformed action of Lorentz group on momentum space... but they also differ from each other from their predictions, DSR1 will be soon tested by AMS and GLAST because of the energy-dependent speed of light while DSR2 does not predict such an effect. For threshold reactions, they both do not solve them, they predict very small corrections to threshold energies. There are a lot of questions and open problems in DSR, the most relevant ones are the following:

Interpretation of mass: In SR the rest energy is identified with the Casimir invariant, in DSR this is no longer the case. For DSR1, the relation between the Casimir invariant m and the rest energy M is

$$m = L_{dsr}^{-1} \left(e^{\frac{L_{dsr} M}{2}} - e^{-\frac{L_{dsr} M}{2}} \right)$$

They start to differ at the order L_{dsr}^2 .

In DSR2

$$m = \frac{M}{1 - L_{dsr} M}$$

They differ already at leading order.

Speed-of-light law: In the absence of a spacetime sector consistent with DSR, it has been argued that the relation between the velocity and the momentum $v = \frac{dE}{dp}$ (or basically the Hamiltonian formulation $\dot{q} = \frac{dH}{dp}$) may not hold in DSR, but in most papers its validity is assumed.

Threshold anomalies: It was hoped that DSR could contribute to resolving the threshold anomalies appearing in some observations. This is not the case, at least for the examples given here. Exploration of other examples could be interesting for this open problem.

In some Lorentz-breaking symmetry scenarios, the corrections appear to be much larger than those in deformation of Lorentz symmetry cases.

Spacetime sector: The natural way to obtain the momentum space, in a relativistic theory with an invariant scale, is to begin with spacetime, defining some quantities in it and doing some manipulations leading to the dispersion relation, as this is done in the formulation of special relativity. For DSR this is reversed, its natural domain is the momentum space, simply because the whole matter is centered on deforming the dispersion relation at Planck scale, which is written in terms of energy and momentum. But it would be lacking in description if it cannot have a spacetime sector, for example the impact of DSR on length contraction is still not clear. Some proposals are under investigation such as κ -Minkowski space.

Macroscopic bodies in DSR: It is still missing how macroscopic bodies are described in such a theory since these typically have energies greater than E_p and yet the observations are in conflict with the assumption of a Planck-scale deformation of the dispersion relation.

Chapter 4

Gravity's rainbow

4.1 Introduction

DSR is intended to be a relativistic theory at Planck scale, encoding properties of flat quantum spacetime. With the loss of linearity in its description on momentum space, the construction of a dual position space becomes nontrivial, for that, some propositions have been made, such as non-commutative spacetime (κ -Minkowski space). The dual space is needed for its generalization in order to include gravitational effects.

Magueijo and Smolin [16] believe that, when taking into account effects of order $l_p E$, there is not just one but many spacetimes, that is, the geometry of spacetime becomes dependent on the energy of the particle moving in it. The energy-dependent family of metrics associated to these spacetimes is referred to be a "rainbow metric", the dual to DSR momentum space would be then the set of spacetimes together with the rainbow metric. This construction should ensure the covariance of the metric under the nonlinear action of Lorentz group implementing DSR and the classical spacetime must be recovered for low energies compared to E_{dsr} .

Construction of a dual space to DSR momentum space (flat rainbow metric):

From DSR2, it was observed that the invariant norm in momentum space takes the form $P^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} U(P^\mu) U(P^\nu)$,

$$U(P) = \begin{bmatrix} fE \\ gP^i \end{bmatrix}$$

$$f = g = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{E}{E_{dsr}}}$$

This has been generalized in [10] by considering different maps $U, U \begin{bmatrix} p^0 \\ p^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f(E)p^0 \\ g(E)p^i \end{bmatrix}$.

The group property is preserved if U is invertible and its image contains $[0, \infty[$.

Thus any isotropic dispersion relation may be written as

$$f^2(E)E^2 - g^2(E)p^2 = m^2$$

In order for this to be translated into the dual position space to DSR momentum space, it is assumed that in the absence of gravity, the geometry of spacetime is probed by the energy of the particle moving in it, where the metric becomes

$\eta(E) = \eta_{\mu\nu}(E)e^\mu e^\nu$. Alternatively, the geometry is given by an energy-dependent basis,

$$e_0^* = \frac{1}{f(E)}e_0, \quad e_i^* = \frac{1}{g(E)}e_i$$

where e_0 and e_i form the usual energy-independent SR basis, the metric is then given by

$$\eta(E) = \eta^{\mu\nu}e_\mu^*e_\nu^*$$

The classical Minkowski space is recovered in the limit $\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow 0$ ($\lim_{\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow \infty} f, g = 1$).

Different observers will see the same particle affected by different metrics since it has different energies according to these observers and for the same observer, different particles with different energies moving in the same region at same time will be affected by different metrics.

Motivations

The above construction is motivated by the fact that free fields in flat spacetime should have plane wave solutions, see [17] for details. So even though P satisfies the deformed dispersion relation, the contraction $x^\mu p_\mu$ must remain linear, that is

$$U(P_\mu)V(x^\mu) = P_\mu x^\mu$$

Which implies that

$$V(x^\mu) = \begin{bmatrix} t \\ \frac{x^i}{g(E)} \end{bmatrix}$$

The transformation on position space must be energy-dependent,

$$t' = \gamma\left(t - vx \frac{f(E)}{g(E)}\right) \frac{f(E')}{f(E)}$$

$$x' = \gamma\left(x - vt \frac{g(E)}{f(E)}\right) \frac{g(E')}{g(E)}$$

$$y' = y \frac{g(E')}{g(E)}$$

$$z' = z \frac{g(E')}{g(E)}$$

The energy-dependent metric invariant under these transformations is then,

$$ds^2 = -\frac{dt^2}{f^2} + \frac{d\mathbf{x}^2}{g^2}$$

4.2 Gravity's rainbow formalism

4.2.1 Modified principles

1. Modified equivalence principle : Within a region of spacetime where the curvature radius $R \gg E_{dsr}^{-1}$, freely falling observers, making measurements of particles with energies $\frac{1}{R} \ll E \ll E_{dsr}^{-1}$, observe the physical laws, to first order in $\frac{1}{R}$, the same as described in DSR. Those freely falling observers will be equivalent to inertial observers of flat rainbow spacetime.
2. Correspondance principle : Classical general relativity is recovered in the limit $\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow 0$.

4.2.2 One parameter family of metrics, connections and curvatures

The modified equivalence principle implies that the spacetime of modified GR is described by a one parameter family of metrics $\{g(E)\}$, $g(E) = g^{\mu\nu}e_\mu(E)e_\nu(E)$
 $e_0(E) = \frac{1}{f(\frac{E}{E_{dsr}})}e_0$, $e_i(E) = \frac{1}{g(\frac{E}{E_{dsr}})}e_i$

$$\lim_{\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow 0} f, g = 1$$

Since the metric is energy-dependent, this implies a one parameter family of connections $\nabla(E)_\mu$ and curvature tensors defined as usual.

4.2.3 Modified Einstein equations

Einstein equations are replaced by a one parameter family of equations by defining also a one parameter family of energy-momentum tensors $T_{\mu\nu}(E)$

$$G_{\mu\nu}(E) - g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda(E) = 8\pi G(E)T_{\mu\nu}(E)$$

where it is expected that both Newton's constant and the cosmological constant become energy-dependent. In the limit $\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow 0$ the physical Newton's constant and cosmological constant are recovered.

Newton's limit

$$\text{Static metric : } g_{00} = -\frac{2\phi}{f^2(E)} - \frac{1}{f^2(E)}, g_{0i} = 0, g_{ij} = \frac{\delta_{ij}}{g^2(E)}$$

$$T_{00} = \frac{\rho}{f^2(E)}, T_{0i} = T_{ij} = 0$$

As a result

$$\partial_i \partial_i \phi = 4\pi G(E)g^2(E)\rho$$

Newton's limit corresponds to $c \rightarrow \infty$, $E_{dsr} \propto \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G}} \rightarrow \infty$, by the correspondence principle $\lim_{\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow 0} G(E) = G(0) = G$ and $\lim_{\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow 0} g = 1$, Hence

$$\partial_i \partial_i \phi = 4\pi G\rho$$

¹ $E \ll E_{dsr}$: for super-Planckian energies, the geometry of spacetime is expected to not have the classical description. $\frac{1}{R} \ll E$: the wavelength of a quanta is much smaller than the radius of curvature.

4.3 Modified solutions

The formalism of gravity's rainbow is illustrated in the examples below

4.3.1 Modified Schwarzschild metric

Beginning with a spherically symmetric gravitational field following the requirements stated previously regarding the metric energy dependence

$$ds^2 = -\frac{e^\nu}{f^2(E)} dt^2 + \frac{e^\lambda}{g^2(E)} dr^2 + \frac{r^2}{g^2(E)} (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\Phi^2)$$

The only modified connection coefficient is

$$\Gamma_{00}^1 = \left(\frac{g}{f}\right)^2 \Gamma_{00}^{1GR}$$

Where Γ_{00}^{1GR} is the connection coefficient of Schwarzschild metric of general relativity. For Ricci tensor, the only modified component is

$$R_{00} = \left(\frac{g}{f}\right)^2 R_{00}^{GR}$$

Similarly here, R_{00}^{GR} is the Ricci component of general relativity. Combining $R_{00} = 0$ and $R_{11} = 0$ gives $\nu + \lambda = 0$. While $R_{22} = 0$ gives

$$g_{00} = -\frac{e^\nu}{f^2} = \frac{-1 - \frac{cst}{r}}{f^2}$$

At $r \rightarrow \infty$, $g_{00} = -\frac{2\phi}{f^2} - \frac{1}{f^2}$ which implies $cst = -2G(0)M$

In consequence,

$$ds^2(E) = \frac{(1 - \frac{2G(0)M}{r})}{f^2(E)} dt^2 + \frac{1}{(1 - \frac{2G(0)M}{r})g^2(E)} dr^2 + \frac{r^2}{g^2(E)} (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\Phi^2)$$

4.3.2 Modified Friedmann-Robertson-Walker metric

The family of FRW metrics are given by

$$ds^2(E) = -\frac{dt^2}{f^2(E)} + \frac{a^2}{g^2} \gamma_{ij} dx^i dx^j$$

The only modified connection components are

$$\Gamma_{ij}^0 = \left(\frac{f}{g}\right)^2 a\dot{a}\gamma_{ij}$$

The modified Ricci components are

$$R_{ij} = \gamma_{ij} \left(\left(\frac{f}{g}\right)^2 (\ddot{a}a + 2\dot{a}^2) + 2k \right)$$

The energy-momentum tensor expression remains the same, the only energy dependent quantity is the four-vector U , $U = (\frac{1}{f(E)}, 0, 0, 0)$. Friedmann equations become then,

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi}{3}G(E)\frac{(\rho + 3p)}{f^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3}$$

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G(E)}{3f^2}\rho - \frac{k}{a^2}\left(\frac{g}{f}\right)^2 + \frac{\Lambda}{3}$$

4.4 Conclusion

Gravity's rainbow is a theory of gravity that originates from finding the dual of DSR momentum space, a construction motivated by requiring linearity to the contraction between position and momentum which, in turn, fixes the transformation in position space letting it to be energy dependent. The metric of this flat spacetime should be energy dependent in order to be invariant under these transformations. This argument carries over to curved spacetime. The exploration of some solutions, namely the cosmological and black hole solutions are useful, in this context, to see the impact of this theory on some problems such as the horizon problem and the implications it may have on black hole thermodynamics.

Conclusion

Doubly special relativity is assumed to be descending from quantum-gravity theory similarly to what special relativity is to general relativity. It is not clear how such a theory could help a formulation of a quantum-gravity theory but it might assist it by providing some insights and numerous characteristics that DSR is enriched with. That is why it was preserved despite the fact that it does not resolve the threshold paradoxes.

The passage from its original formulation as a nonlinear realization of Lorentz group on momentum space to shaping the momentum space as a De Sitter space provides gain in some flexibility on finding various models of DSR theory by building different coordinate systems as well as constructing different phase spaces corresponding to DSR by choosing different decompositions of the algebra of symmetries of De Sitter momentum space. The other approach, namely the κ -Poincaré algebra, is motivated by the fact that the Poincaré group should be extended in analogy to special relativity where the Galilean group was extended to Poincaré group in order to include the speed of light as an observer independent scale. In this way, the new Planck scale κ is included as a second observer independent scale.

The ascending from DSR to gravity's rainbow is a plus, the energy-dependent metric formulation may be useful to be compared with other theories of gravity that would follow from other realizations of position space and see what are the most significant physical consequences which can be extracted from them.

Appendix

.1 Calculation of GZK limit

UHECR: reaction $p\gamma \rightarrow p\pi$

Conservation law : $P_p + P_\gamma = P'_p + P_\pi$

The threshold energy is the lowest proton's energy allowing the production of $\gamma\pi$, which means that these later are produced at rest in their center of mass frame.

Squaring both sides of the conservation law, taking the right side of the equation in the laboratory frame while the left side in the center of mass of $\gamma\pi$, no worries about this since spacetime intervals are invariant

$$(P_p + P_\gamma)^2 = (P'_p + P_\pi)^2$$

$$(P'_p + P_\pi)^2 = -(m_p + m_\pi)^2 c^2$$

$$(P_p + P_\gamma)^2 = P_p^2 + 2P_p \cdot P_\gamma + P_\gamma^2 = -m_p^2 c^2 + 2P_p P_\gamma + P_\gamma^2$$

evaluating the term $P_p P_\gamma$,

$$P_p = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_p}{c} \\ \frac{\vec{p}_p}{c} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P_\gamma = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_\gamma}{c} \\ \frac{\vec{p}_\gamma}{c} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where it is assumed that the collision happens in a highly relativistic regime, so that $p_p = \frac{E_p}{c}$ and for simplicity, the momenta of the two particles are taken in opposite directions.

$$P_p \cdot P_\gamma = -2 \frac{E_p E_\gamma}{c^2}$$

as a result,

$$E_p = \frac{(m_p + m_\pi)^2 c^4 - m_p^2 c^4}{4E_\gamma}$$

Remark : The same method applies for the second possible reaction of UHECR $p\gamma \rightarrow n\pi^+$ and for the gamma-ray reaction $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow e^-e^+$.

$$p\gamma \rightarrow p\pi^0$$

$$E_p = 1.06 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ eV}$$

$$p\gamma \rightarrow n\pi^+$$

$$E_p = 1.03 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ eV}$$

$$\gamma\gamma \rightarrow e^-e^+$$

$$E_\gamma = 3.94 \cdot 10^8 \text{ eV}$$

.2 DSR calculations

To show that the modified dispersion relation is not invariant under the SR boost generator, the commutator of the SR boost with the modified dispersion relation is calculated

$$[B_i^{SR}, E^2 - p^2 - L_{dsr}p^2E] = -p_i L_{dsr}p^2E - 2E^2p_i L_{dsr}$$

The commutator is not equal to zero, therefore the dispersion relation is not invariant. The terms which should be added to the boost are the ones that eliminate the terms resulted from the calculated commutator:

$$\frac{L_{dsr}p^2}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i}, -L_{dsr}p_i(p_k \frac{\partial}{\partial p_k}) \text{ to eliminate } -p_i L_{dsr}p^2E$$

$$-E^2 L_{dsr} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} \text{ to eliminate } -2E^2p_i L_{dsr}.$$

The modified boost generator takes the form,

$$B_i = B_i^{SR} + \frac{L_{dsr}p^2}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} - E^2 c^{-2} L_{dsr} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} - L_{dsr}p_i(p_k \frac{\partial}{\partial p_k})$$

The invariance of the modified dispersion under this boost generator can be checked to leading order

$$[B_i, E^2 - p^2 - L_{dsr}p^2E] = 0$$

This can also be checked for all-order DSR1 and DSR2 dispersion relations under their corresponding boost generators.

Conservation rules

Denoting $P_4 = \begin{bmatrix} E \\ p \end{bmatrix}$ the physical energy-momentum that transform under DSR

transformation and introducing $\mathcal{P}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon \\ \pi \end{bmatrix}$ the pseudo energy-momentum that trans-

form like a Lorentz 4-vector in the usual linear manner $\mathcal{L} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon \\ \pi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon' \\ \pi' \end{bmatrix}$

$$P_4 = F(\mathcal{P}_4), \quad \mathcal{P}_4 = F^{-1}(P_4)$$

F and F^{-1} are nonlinear functions.

$$\lim_{\frac{E}{E_{dsr}} \rightarrow 0} F, F^{-1} = I_d \Rightarrow P_4 = \mathcal{P}_4$$

$$P'_4 = L(P_4) = (F \circ \mathcal{L} \circ F^{-1})(P_4)$$

Recall that in SR, the composition of momenta is linear

$$\mathcal{P}_4^{tot} = \sum_i \mathcal{P}_4^i$$

or implicitly

$$P_4^{tot} = F\left(\sum_i F^{-1}(P_4^i)\right)$$

so the general composition of 4-momenta is based on iterating an associative symmetric binary function which is applied in the context of DSR. In the case of DSR2,

$$\mathcal{P}_4 = (\epsilon, \pi) = F^{-1}(P_4) = \frac{(E, P)}{1 - L_{dsr}E}$$

The inverse is

$$P_4 = (E, P) = F(\mathcal{P}_4) = \frac{(\epsilon, \pi)}{1 + L_{dsr}E}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon^{tot} &= \sum_i \frac{E_i}{1 - L_{dsr}E_i} \\ \pi^{tot} &= \sum_i \frac{P_i}{1 - L_{dsr}E_i}\end{aligned}$$

The conservation rules for DSR2 are then

$$\begin{aligned}E^{tot} = F(\epsilon^{tot}) &= \frac{\sum_i \frac{E_i}{1 - L_{dsr}E_i}}{1 + L_{dsr} \sum_i \frac{E_i}{1 - L_{dsr}E_i}} = 0 \\ P^{tot} = F(\pi^{tot}) &= \frac{\sum_i \frac{P_i}{1 - L_{dsr}E_i}}{1 + L_{dsr} \sum_i \frac{P_i}{1 - L_{dsr}E_i}} = 0\end{aligned}$$

In the DSR1 case :

Given the transformation rules

$$\begin{aligned}e^{L_{dsr}E} &= e^{L_{dsr}M}(1 + \sin(L_{dsr}M)e^{-L_{dsr}M}(\cosh\phi - 1)) \\ p &= \frac{1}{L_{dsr}} \frac{\sinh(L_{dsr}M)e^{-L_{dsr}M}\sinh\phi}{1 + \sinh(L_{dsr}M)e^{-L_{dsr}M}(\cosh\phi - 1)}\end{aligned}$$

Which can be inverted into

$$\begin{aligned}\sinh\phi &= \frac{pL_{dsr}e^{L_{dsr}E}}{\sinh(L_{dsr}M)} \\ \cosh\phi &= \frac{e^{L_{dsr}E} - \cosh(L_{dsr}M)}{\sinh(L_{dsr}M)}\end{aligned}$$

Using $\cosh^2\phi - \sinh^2\phi = 1$

$$\cosh L_{dsr}E = \cosh L_{dsr}M + \frac{L_{dsr}^2 p^2 e^{L_{dsr}E}}{2}$$

The relation between the rest energy and the Casimir invariant is then

$$\cosh(L_{dsr}M) = 1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2 m^2}{2} \quad m = \frac{2\sinh(L_{dsr}M/2)}{L_{dsr}}$$

It follows that

$$\epsilon = m \cosh\phi = \frac{e^{L_{dsr}E} - \cosh(L_{dsr}M)}{L_{dsr} \cosh(L_{dsr}M/2)}$$

$$\pi = m \sinh\phi = \frac{p e^{L_{dsr}E}}{\cosh(L_{dsr}M/2)}$$

Conversely,

$$E = \frac{1}{L_{dsr}} \ln(L_{dsr} \epsilon \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4}(\epsilon^2 - \pi^2)} + 1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{2}(\epsilon^2 - \pi^2))$$

$$p = \frac{\pi \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4}(\epsilon^2 - \pi^2)}}{L_{dsr} \epsilon \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4}(\epsilon^2 - \pi^2)} + 1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{2}(\epsilon^2 - \pi^2)}$$

The conservation rules are then

$$E^{tot} = \frac{1}{L_{dsr}} \ln[L_{dsr} \epsilon^{tot} \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4}((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)} + 1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{2}((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)] = 0$$

$$p^{tot} = \frac{\pi^{tot} \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4}((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)}}{L_{dsr} \epsilon^{tot} \sqrt{1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{4}((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)} + 1 + \frac{L_{dsr}^2}{2}((\epsilon^{tot})^2 - (\pi^{tot})^2)} = 0$$

With

$$\epsilon^{tot} = \sum_i \frac{e^{L_{dsr}E_i} - \cosh(L_{dsr}M_{,i})}{L_{dsr} \cosh(L_{dsr}M_{,i}/2)}$$

$$\pi^{tot} = \sum_i \frac{p_i e^{L_{dsr}E_i}}{\cosh(L_{dsr}M_{,i}/2)}$$

Calculation of thresholds

In order to estimate the phenomenological implications of deformed Lorentz invariance, it is convenient to do the calculations fully in the laboratory frame. For instance, the SR formula for the threshold reaction $p_{1,th} = \frac{(m_3+m_4)^2 - m_1^2}{4E_2}$ may be obtained by using the usual conservation rules and the approximated dispersion relation

$$E = p + \frac{m^2}{2p}$$

Where the approximation comes from the fact that p_1 is very large.

DSR1: using leading-order conservation rules and the approximated dispersion relation

$$E = p + \frac{m^2}{2p} + \frac{L_{dsr} p^2}{2}$$

DSR2: using leading-order conservation rules and the leading order dispersion relation

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2 - 2L_{dsr}E(E^2 - p^2)$$

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